

and yield. At harvest, rice had a significant plant height reduction of 9-12% and tiller number reduction of 18-24%. The pure stand of upland rice yielded 2.8 t/ha; intercropped rice showed significant yield reduction. Reduced plant height, tiller number, and grain yield was correlated positively with

Lamtoro cumulative dry weight.

The results suggest a negative interaction between Lamtoro cultivars and intercropped upland rice with the 2 m row spacing. Row spacing should be adjusted for optimum rice yield.

A decrease in exchangeable A1+H and A1 saturation and an increase in

exchangeable Ca+Mg occurred in the intercropped plots. Intercropping upland rice and Lamtoro and returning Lamtoro biomass to the soil over a period of several years may actually result in decreased A1 and increased plant nutrients in the soil. □

Cumulative dry weight of Lamtoro after 3 cuttings, growth and yield of intercropped upland rice, and soil chemical properties after rice harvest.^a Sumatra, Indonesia, 1983-84.

Lamtoro variety	Cumulative dry weight (t/ha)	Upland rice plant height (cm)			Upland rice tillers (no./hill)			Upland rice grain yield (t/ha)	Exchangeable A1+H (meq/100 g)	Exchangeable Ca+Mg (meq/100 g)	A1 saturation (%)
		30 DAS	60 DAS	Harvest	30 DAS	60 DAS	Harvest				
Peru	4.6 a	43 a	73 a	111 c	19 a	34 a	13 b	2.1 b	3.9 ab	0.8 a	82 ab
K-8	5.2 a	45 a	74 a	120 ab	20 a	37 a	14 b	2.4 b	3.8 ab	0.8 a	82 ab
K-28	6.3 a	47 a	76 a	120 ab	18 a	38 a	14 b	1.7 c	2.8 b	1.5 b	63 b
Gung	4.7 a	41 a	69 a	115 bc	17 a	39 a	14 b	2.1 b	3.5 ab	0.9 a	84 a
Control	-	42 a	79 a	126 a	21 a	36 a	17 a	2.8 a	4.0 a	0.7 a	85 a

^aDAS = days after seeding. Data are means of 4 replications. Mean separation by DMRT at 5%.

Performance of transplanted aman rice varieties in cropping pattern trials

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We evaluated six T. aman rice varieties in cropping pattern trials in the 1982-1983 late wet seasons. The Hathazari cropping systems site is medium high land. The objective was to identify short-duration varieties with higher yields at low fertilizer levels in the broadcast aus - T. aman - cowpea cropping pattern under rainfed conditions.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with five replications across farms. Each year, 37-d-old seedlings were transplanted 24-27 Aug at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 60-17.6-16.6 kg NPK/ha.

The varieties exhibited significant variations in yield, days to flowering, and days to maturity (see table).

BR11 is resistant to lodging and shattering, with medium grains. Its market value is higher because its grains produce quality rice and pop. □

Performance of T. aman varieties in farmers' cropping patterns at Hathazari, Bangladesh, 1982-83.^a

Variety	Flowering (DT)		Maturity (DT)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1982	1983	1982	1983	1982	1983
BR3	68 b	70 ab	109 b	112 b	3.2 a	3.5 ab
BR4	65 c	67 bc	106 bc	109 bc	2.6 ab	3.0 b
BR10	64 c	66 c	106 bc	108 c	3.2 a	3.4 b
BR11	62 d	64 c	101 c	108 c	3.2 a	4.3 a
Pajam	56 e	59 d	97 d	101 d	2.8 a	2.7 b
Chakkal (check)	72 a	73 a	114 a	117 a	2.0 b	2.8 b
CV (%)	2.7	4.6	2.9	2.1	19.8	20.0

^aDT = days after transplanting.

SOCIOECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Production

Economics of rice gall midge (GM) management in resistant and susceptible cultures

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We studied the incidence of GM in three resistant and one GM-susceptible cultivars with and without pest management in a split-plot design with three replications during the 1986 wet season.

GM incidence in the susceptible variety crossed the economic threshold (ETL) 48 d after transplanting (DT)

and again 68 DT. Incidence in the 3 resistant varieties did not cross ETL, but leafhopper incidence crossed ETL at 68 DT.

In the pest management plots, the susceptible variety received two sprayings; the resistant varieties received one. Phosalone 35 EC at 1.5 liters/ha

was sprayed 48 DT, monocrotophos 36 WSC at 500 ml/ha was sprayed 68 DT. GM incidence was calculated as percentage affected tillers.

GM incidence among the three GM-resistant varieties was significantly lower in IET8649 and higher in IET6315 (see table). The three GM-resistant varieties

that received only one spraying gave higher yield and income than the GM-susceptible variety with two sprayings.

Yield of GM-susceptible variety Sona was on a par with that of GM-resistant varieties IET8649 and 6315. Highest income was from GM-resistant variety IET8655 (1:12.12 cost-benefit ratio). □

Economics of the use of GM-resistant and susceptible cultures.^a

Culture	GM incidence (%) 80 DT			Grain yield (t/ha)			Added returns due to PM (\$/ha)	Cost of PM (\$/ha)	Added net returns due to PM (\$/ha)	Cost-to-benefit ratio
	PM	No PM	Mean	PM	No PM	Mean				
<i>GM-resistant</i>										
IET8649	1.7 (7.9)	2.0 (8.4)	1.85 a (8.15)	6.40	5.83	6.12 b	89.7	9.8	79.9	1:8.12
IET8655	3.8 (11.7)	3.2 (10.9)	3.50 b (11.30)	8.22	7.40	7.81 a	129.1	9.8	119.3	1:12.12
IET6315	4.8 (13.2)	7.1 (15.7)	5.95 c (14.45)	7.02	6.45	6.74 b	89.7	9.8	79.9	1:8.12
<i>GM-susceptible</i>										
Sona	11.4 (20.1)	18.6 (25.5)	15.00 d (22.80)	5.93	5.72	5.83 b	33.1	24.8	8.3	Loss
Mean ^b	5.4 (13.2)	7.7 (15.1)		6.89 b	6.35 a					

^aFigures in parentheses are arc sine values. PM = pest management, no PM = no pest management. Means in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

ANNOUNCEMENTS

Deepwater rice workshop examines innovative cropping

The Deepwater Rice Workshop in Bangkok, Thailand, 26-30 Oct 1987 was cosponsored by IRRI and the Thai Department of Agriculture and the Rice Research Institute of the Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives. The 79 participants and 36 observers from 16 countries included trainees in the special Genetic Evaluation and Utilization Training Course for Deepwater Rice and participants in the Deepwater Rice Monitoring Tour that visited Vietnam, India, and Thailand. Discussion groups on research priorities, methodology, breeding strategies, and terminology made recommendations for future action.

The workshop produced a number of innovative ideas, such as additional crops (sunflower, early-maturing rice, etc.) before, with, or after the deepwater

rice crop; ratooning the deepwater rice; use of rice herbage from the deepwater rice crop; methods for screening against *ufra* nematode and yellow stem borer; and methods for measuring oxygen, carbon dioxide, and ethylene in floodwater.

IRRI will publish the proceedings. □

1987 International Rice Research Conference

Nearly 100 participants from 19 countries met 21-25 Sep 1987 in Hangzhou, China. The focus was on irrigated rice. Discussions spanned the global rice situation, physiological aspects of yielding ability, disease, insect, and weed management; nutrient management; water management and farming systems; innovative breeding; grain quality; farm machinery and postharvest management; and collaborative research relationships.

Extensive recommendations for research and related priorities were made in all areas.

A highlight of the conference was the dedication of the China National Rice Research Center research facilities and buildings at the experimental farm site. National Minister of Agriculture, Animal Husbandry, and Fishery He Kang addressed the conference during opening ceremonies.

A proceedings including selected key papers and abstracts of the 64 papers presented will be published by IRRI in late 1988. □

Gene banks and the world's food

Gene banks and the world's food by D.L. Plucknett, N.J.H. Smith, J.T. Williams, and N.M. Anishetty provides a history of germplasm preservation and exchange (from botanical gardens to modern cold-storage units) and an assessment of the scientific and political ramifications of gene bank programs. It contributes to the debate on how best to